

Distally Pedicled Brachioradialis Rotational Muscle Flap for Reconstruction of A Complex Post-traumatic Anterior Elbow Defect -A Simple to plan, Quick to Harvest and Easy-to-Do Flap. A Rare Case Report.

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ABSTRACT

The reconstruction of post-traumatic anterior elbow defects with exposed joint and neurovascular structures is a challenging problem. We report a 32 year old male who suffered a road traffic accident (RTA) and was admitted as a case of exsanguinating left upper limb, with unstable hemodynamics, having contaminated, complex anterior elbow defect with exposed joint and neurovascular structures and we successfully reconstructed the defect with a distally based brachioradialis muscle flap.

Keywords: Muscle; Elbow; Neurovascular

INTRODUCTION

Elbow trauma may result in loss of the overlying soft tissue resulting in exposure of the antecubital neurovascular structures and the elbow flexor tendons and in severe cases the joint because of the thin soft tissue cover and relatively superficial location of these structures. These soft tissue defects pose challenging problem because of their critical location.^[1] A healthy and durable soft tissue coverage of these defects is very important to restore the form, function, contour and cosmesis of the upper limb. Many loco-regional and distant flaps have been used to reconstruct these defects. Local flaps as proximally pedicled fasciocutaneous radial artery flap (RAF) is a good option but needs sacrifice of radial artery, a major blood vessel supplying hand, which may affect the distal vascularity. Distant flaps like thoracoabdominal wall flaps need prolonged immobilization of the shoulder joint besides being two stage surgical procedures. Prolonged immobilization may end up in stiffness of the upper limb joints especially the shoulder joint. Free tissue transfer is an amazing reconstructive option but is technically demanding ,need expertise and surgical operative microscope facilities.^[2] Among the local options, the brachioradialis muscle flap is well vascularized which provides healthy stable soft tissue coverage. According to Mathes Nahai muscle flap classification, the brachioradialis is a Type II muscle flap with the major pedicle arising from the radial recurrent artery in 42% , radial artery in 38% and brachial arteries in 20% cases and maximum of three minor muscle branches at variable positions from the radial artery. ^[2] The muscular branch of the radial recurrent artery is about 3 cm long with a diameter of 2 mm and exits from the radial artery at the medial border of the muscle about 10 cm from the origin of the muscle.^[3] The muscle is around 34 cm long with the muscle belly being 22 cm and the tendon around 12 cm in length. The muscle belly is 3.5 cm wide and 1 to 2.5 cm thick.^[2] Usually 9 by 10 cm² flap cover is provided by the muscle which is sufficient to cover either the antecubital fossa, the forearm neurovascular structures, or an area of soft tissue loss.^[4] Spreading the muscle by incising the perimysium along the long axis in the direction of muscle fibers adds one-third of the extra width.^[5] The brachioradialis muscle was used in the past as a proximally based muscle flap. ^[6,7] However here we describe its use as distally pedicled flap with reverse blood flow from the radial artery and other surrounding perforators.

CASE REPORT

A 32 year old married male driver by profession, with no significant past medical and surgical history who presented to the emergency department (ED) of our hospital with trauma to left upper limb hours after sustaining the injury following road traffic accident (RTA). The patient had bled diffusely from the wound before his arrival to the hospital. Immediately after the patient arrival, trauma resuscitation protocol including airway, breathing, and circulation (ABC) assessment was performed according to latest advanced trauma life support (ATLS) guidelines. After securing a IV line with a grey cannula, patient was given optimal analgesia to control pain, intravenous fluids, broad spectrum antibiotics (BSA) and a blood sample was taken for laboratory tests including hematology, blood grouping and cross match and serum chemistry. Patient also received tetanus prophylaxis. The hemodynamics of the patient was maintained with a

pulse rate of 98 beats per minute and a blood pressure of 100/60 mmHg. After pain control, the patient was examined for the left upper limb injury and findings of composite tissue loss involving antecubital fossa, leaving neurovascular structures exposed, and the forearm with the hand were noted. [Photo 1]. Complete blood count (CBC) was showing a hemoglobin value of 10 g/dl. After taking a consent for surgery, the patient was urgently shifted to emergency operation theatre for assessment of the injury and the required surgical intervention. The patient was placed in the supine position and underwent general anesthesia with orotracheal intubation. A mid-arm pneumatic tourniquet was applied. The patient was jointly operated by teams of vascular surgery and plastic surgery. The part was sterilely prepped and draped. Saline irrigation of the wounds was done to remove the blood clots to enable proper assessment of the depth of the injury. On surgical exploration, the intra-operative findings were an excavating wound due to soft tissue loss with complete transection of the radial artery, with segmental loss, just after its origin from the brachial artery, exposed neurovascular structures including median nerve, brachial artery, radial nerve, elbow flexors and a rent in the anterior capsule of the elbow joint. [Photo 2] Sharp surgical debridement of both the elbow and the hand wounds was done. The transected radial artery was ligated by the vascular surgery team after doubly confirming the distal arterial flow by the intraoperative doppler. The rent in the elbow joint was repaired with prolene 2-0 suture. A distally based rotational brachioradialis muscle flap was raised by cutting the origin of the muscle from the lateral supracondylar ridge of the humerus and continuing the dissection distally till a flap of required length was harvested. The vascularity of the flap was checked repeatedly and remained intact during the whole process of harvesting. Since the radial artery was already cut just at its origin from the brachial artery and also we didn't encounter any feeding vessel to the brachioradialis from the brachial artery while raising the flap we presume the radial artery perforators supply the flap from the reverse flow maintained through the patent vascular palmar arch as confirmed by the intraoperative doppler. We incised the perimysium of the muscle along its axis to gain extra width to cover the defect adequately. [Photo 3] The flap inset was given by vicryl 2-0 suture. A 14 size suction drain was put in the donor site and complete hemostasis was achieved. Skin graft harvested from the left thigh was meshed (1:1.5) and applied over the muscle flap and the raw area over the hand [Photo 4]. A moist dressing using supra-tulle was applied followed by a back slab with elbow in 20 degree flexion. The first dressing was done on 3rd post-operative day (POD) and patient was discharged after second dressing and advised to follow up out patient department (OPD). On follow up visit after 6 weeks the skin graft was well settled, the back slab was removed and the patient was referred to physiotherapy department. [Photo5]

Photo 1: Pre-operative picture showing the excavated wound with soft tissue loss involving the cubital fossa with surrounding forearm abrasions.

Photo 2: Intra-operative picture showing anterior left elbow defect with exposed median nerve, brachial artery with ligated radial artery, elbow flexors and the superficial radial nerve. (medial to lateral)

Photo 3: Intra-operative picture showing the distally based rotational brachioradialis muscle flap covering the anterior elbow defect.

Photo 4: Intra-operative picture showing the meshed (1:1.5) skin graft applied over the muscle flap.

Photo 5: Post operative picture on follow up showing a well settled graft.

DISCUSSION

Because of the superficial placement of the neurovascular structures especially the brachial artery, injuries of the cubital fossa pose a difficult problem as these injuries inevitably result in exposure of these vital structures and if not covered timely may lead to medial necrosis of the vessels, aneurysm formation and rupture. So, it is very important to reconstruct these defects with adequate durable soft tissue coverage.^[8] Split thickness skin graft (STSG) is not a stable coverage in the presence of exposed vital structures or the joint itself besides it may lead to failure of the graft take, unstable scar formation or flexion contracture of the elbow. There is limited choice of local fasciocutaneous flaps in this region especially when the zone of the trauma is extensive. In our case the radial artery was artery cut because of the trauma which precluded the use of proximally based radial forearm flap. Also as the patient got hemodynamically unstable during the intraoperative period we did not opt for the lateral arm flap as the dissection is tedious, time consuming as against the brachioradialis flap. Distant flaps are not a good choice in these cases especially in the presence of external fixators for the associated fracture dislocation of the elbow joint besides require two stage procedures and may end up in stiffness of the upper limb joints especially the shoulder joint in the elderly people. Because of the associated vascular injury in the form of transection, contusion or vessel wall tear or intimal injury in these cases the success of free tissue transfer is doubtful.^[9,10] The advantage of using the brachioradialis muscle flap in

these defects is that it is just adjacent to the defect itself, is technically easy and less time consuming to harvest, reliable and drapes the defect well because of its pliability besides reduces the risk of infections in contaminated wounds because of better vascularity. With distally pedicled brachioradialis the proximal muscle belly readily conforms the defect eliminating the dead space, minimizes the risk of infection, provides adequate tissue for coverage and gives better contour.

CONCLUSION

The distally pedicled brachioradialis muscle flap is reliable, simple to plan, quick to harvest, easy to do flap with the proximal muscle belly providing adequate durable cover conforming well to the defect thereby restoring the form, function and the cosmesis with relatively lesser donor site morbidity.

Level of evidence (LOE): IV

Conflict of interest: Nil

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